

**CURRENT STATE OF INVESTMENT ENVIRONMENT IN
UZBEKISTAN**

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One of the most effective ways to achieve the economic development of our country, the increase in the level of well-being of its population, and at the same time, the emergence of a globally competitive and stable developing country, is to attract foreign and domestic investments to the country. The relevance of investment activities is that investments are any means that preserve the value of money or increase its value and help to obtain positive returns. That is, the investment market creates conditions for the organization and financing of investments. The main elements are demand, supply, competition and price. Therefore, investment and financial rights have a special place in the development and promotion of the country's economy. For this reason, it contributes to the creation of conditions for the formation of a democratic, legal state and a strong civil society, as well as legal and economic opportunities for business entities.

It is known that any country in the world cannot achieve development and economic development without attracting foreign investments. That is why this work has become one of the priorities in the economic and legal policy of our country. We should also mention that the existing legislation in our country provides a number of guarantees and benefits to foreign investors in this regard. At this point, recognizing the importance of foreign investments in our economy, it is necessary to win the trust of foreign investors in the investment policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the rule of law, and most importantly, as a strong partner capable of solvency.

As the President of our country, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, said: "World experience shows that any country that has pursued an active investment policy has achieved stable growth of its economy. That's why investment is the driver of the economy, it is no exaggeration to say that it is the heart of the economy in Uzbek terms. Along with investment, new technologies, advanced experiences, and highly qualified specialists enter various industries and sectors, regions, and entrepreneurship develops rapidly [1]". In addition, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" defines the following priority

directions for investment: "Strengthening of macroeconomic stability aimed at further development and liberalization of the economy and maintain high economic growth rates, increase the competitiveness of the national economy, modernize and rapidly develop agriculture, continue institutional and structural reforms to reduce state participation in the economy, protect the right to private property and its priority position further strengthening, stimulating the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, comprehensive and proportionate socio-economic development of regions, districts and cities, actively attracting foreign investments to the sectors and regions of our country's economy by improving the investment environment" thereby improving the investment environment of Uzbekistan and great attention is being paid to the development of its potential. In attracting and regulating foreign investments in Uzbekistan, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Investments and Investment Activities" dated December 9, 2019 and other legal documents serve as its legal basis. An active policy aimed at accelerating the attraction of foreign investments is being carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Ensuring the conversion of the national currency according to current operations and the strategy of implementing reforms will form a favorable basis for further liberalization of the economy in Uzbekistan and the implementation of projects with the participation of foreign capital. A comprehensive system of legal guarantees and benefits for foreign investors has been formed in our republic. This system is based on the "On measures to attract foreign investments and loans and improvement of the development process" on attracting foreign and local investments, "On investments and investment activities" on protecting the rights of investors, and on attracting shares " Based on the laws on the stock market. These laws ensure that foreign investors operate under equal and fair conditions. In addition, a system of additional measures, including tax breaks and preferences, has been developed to encourage the activities of foreign-invested enterprises. The investment environment depends on the region's availability of labor resources with certain qualifications and education, production, financial and innovative potential, institutional environment and infrastructure of the region. The third group includes factors related to investment risk, which have the potential to have a large impact on investment attractiveness in the short and medium term. In order to assess the investment attractiveness of the region, it is appropriate to take into account its economic, social, financial, management, environmental and political risks. The same factors allow foreign investors to invest their resources

in another country on the basis of long-term contracts. Such an environment is very important in the implementation of long-term investment plans. The purpose of this work is to study the origin evolution, characteristics and problems of international investment law, to determine the role of international conventions and agreements as sources of international investment law, and to analyze the extent to which it will develop in the future. To achieve this goal, we must solve the following tasks:

- Analysis of the evolution of international investment law;
- Reveal the concept and features of international investment law;
- Analysis of international investment law problems;
- Review of the development process of international investments.

Nowadays, international investment law is gaining urgent importance. If we analyze the relevance of this right depending on a number of circumstances, first of all, international investment law as a small branch of economic law began to be formed recently. The development of international investment law took place in several complex stages, and I think that their study is of fundamental importance for us, because each such stage is formed by the formation of a certain base of international treaties and agreements. Secondly, today there are many problems in the international investment law, one of them is the provision of legal protection of foreign investments. Currently, there are 21 free economic zones (SEZs) in the Republic of Uzbekistan, of which 19 are specialized in industry, 1 in agriculture and 1 in tourism.

In the period from 2008 to 2021, a total of 448 projects worth 2.4 billion dollars were implemented in the territories of free economic zones. Of the total amount, 764.6 million dollars are foreign direct investments. About 34,000 new

jobs were created at the expense of the projects. The three largest of these projects are:

1. "Angren" SEZ - 73 projects worth 730.7 million dollars.
2. "Urgut" SEZ - 55 projects worth 312.9 million dollars.
3. "Navoiy" SEZ - 53 projects worth 282.8 million dollars were implemented.

By the end of 2020, 128 projects with a total value of 487.4 million dollars were implemented in the SEZ territories. Of this, 162.1 million dollars are foreign direct investments. We can see the number of projects and their value in money in the following diagram.

As a sovereign state, Uzbekistan creates wide legal and economic opportunities for international attention, development of world economic relations and, on this basis, lays the foundation for the economic and social development of the society.

Today, it is a priority to ensure a favorable investment climate in Uzbekistan. The main task of the state is to create a favorable investment environment for attracting capital. Currently, the Republic of Uzbekistan has the opportunity to attract a large amount of foreign investments:

- on the basis of legal documents that reflect guarantees and benefits
- in the economy through the private sector and small business
- increasing share of private entrepreneurship
- state protection of private property
- existence of a competitive environment
- creation of necessary investment infrastructure
- developing; political stability

- medium level of geographical location
- possession of rich natural mineral raw materials
- development of the agricultural sector;
- availability of cheap and qualified labor resources.

In our opinion, in order to develop the favorable investment environment created in the republic, it is necessary to further strengthen the incentive factors. In this regard, in order to encourage investment in production, it is necessary to give full freedom to business structures in the application of accelerated depreciation methods. In the conditions of the market economy, depreciation is one of the main factors stimulating the investment activity of enterprises. Therefore, in developed countries, the rate of depreciation is determined simultaneously with the approval of the tax rate. In this case, high depreciation rates are set to encourage investment in leading sectors.

List of used literature:

1. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis on the most important priority tasks for 2019. People's word, December 29, 2018
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on "Strategy of actions on five priority directions of further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", PD-4947.
3. Botirjon oglu, M. B., & Hasanboy oglu, S. D. (2022). ORGANIZATION AND INCREASE OF ACTIVITY OF SMALL INDUSTRIAL ZONES
4. Joraboyev Haliljon. "WAYS OF FORMING THE INVESTMENT ENVIRONMENT AND MAIN ISSUES OF IMPROVEMENT"
5. Rashidov O. Y., Kurbanov X. A., Karlibayeva. R. Kh., Organization and financing of investments: Study guide. - T.: Publishing House of the Literary Fund of the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan, 2005. - 128 p.
6. Umarov U. A., Financial law: textbook. - T.: Tafakkur bostoni, 2017 - 8p.
7. Холмаматов, Ф. К. (2024). ТИЖОРАТ БАНКЛАРИДА ЛИКВИДЛИК РИСКНИ БОШҚАРИШ АМАЛИЁТИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ ОРҚАЛИ МОЛИЯВИЙ БАРҚАРОРЛИГИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШ: Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari. Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari, 5(1), 375-382.
8. Navruzov, I. (2022). MILLIY IQTISODIYOTGA TO'G'RIDAN-TO'G'RI XORIJIY INVESTITSİYALARNI JALB QILISHNI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI. Iqtisodiyot va ta'lim, 23(6), 297-300.

9. Qizi, Aminova Nilufar Umarboy. "ISSUES OF FINANCING OF INVESTMENT PROJECTS ON THE BASIS OF SYNDICATE LOANING." Open Access Repository 10.12 (2023): 8-14.
10. Suleymanov, Inur. "FEATURES OF FINANCIAL SUPPORT FOR THE REAL SECTOR OF UZBEKISTAN'S ECONOMY IN THE CONTEXT OF GEO-FINANCIAL POLICY INSTABILITY." Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development 23 (2024): 33-43.
11. Холмаматов, Ф. К. "Тижорат банкларининг кредитлаш амалиётини такомиллаштириш. И. ф. б. ф. д. дисс. автореф." И. ф. б. ф. д. илм. дар. ол. уч. тақд. эт. дисс. автореф.–Тошкент (2019).
12. Suleymanov, Inur. "CHALLENGES IN ENHANCING THE RESOURCE FOUNDATION OF COMMERCIAL BANKS THROUGH THE INTEGRATION OF BANKING SYSTEMS WITH THE REAL ECONOMY SECTOR." (2024).
13. Холмаматов Ф. К., АМАЛИЁТИНИ Т., ТАЪМИНЛАШ Т. О. М. Б. Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari //Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari. – 2024. – Т. 5. – №. 1. – С. 375-382.
14. Сулейманов, Ильнур, and Дмитрий Рахимов. "НАЛОГОВАЯ ПОЛИТИКА В ФИНАНСОВО-ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ГРУППАХ." Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences 3.4 (2024): 33-38.
15. Хошимов С. АНАЛИЗ СТРАХОВАНИЯ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ИНВЕСТИЦИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ //Iqtisodiyot va ta'lim. – 2022. – Т. 23. – №. 1. – С. 119-124.
16. Хошимов Ж. Р., Очиллов Б. Б., Наримонов С. С. ИНВЕСТИЦИОННАЯ ПОЛИТИКА: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА. – 2024.
17. Сулейманов, И. ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЕ МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ ФИНАНСОВЫХ ОТНОШЕНИЙ НА БАНКОВСКИЙ И РЕАЛЬНЫЙ СЕКТОРА ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА В УСЛОВИЯХ ГЕО-ФИНАНСОВОЙ НЕСТАБИЛЬНОСТИ.
18. Ochilov V., Hoshimov J., Butayev J. IQTISODIYOTGA XORIJIY INVESTITSİYALARNI JALB ETISHDA MAMLAKAT INVESTITSION JOZIBADORLIGI: NAZARIYA VA AMALIYOT (Monografiya). – 2024.
19. Tursunkulovich S. R. et al. INCREASING THE LEVEL OF CAPITALIZATION AS A BASIS FOR STRENGTHENING FINANCIAL STABILITY IN COMMERCIAL BANKS //European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development. – 2022. – Т. 4. – С. 201-207.
20. Tursunkulovich S. R. SOME THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL EXPERIENCES REGULATION OF MONEY SUPPLY //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2023. – Т. 16. – С. 60-71.

